

Mawangdui Laozi 馬王堆老子

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Mawangdui Laozi 馬王堆老子 is the name attributed to two silk manuscripts excavated from Mawangdui tomb n. 3 during an archaeological expedition in the small village of Mawangdui, in the outskirts of the city of Changsha 長沙, Hunan 湖南 province. These two silk texts represent some of the earliest versions (with the exception of the three Laozi bamboo bundles excavated from Guodian tomb n. 1) of the text later known as the Daodejing 道德經 ("Classic of the Way and Virtue") and are also known under the name Laozi boshu 老子帛書 (Laozi silk manuscripts). The two manuscripts are now preserved at the Hunan Provincial Museum (湖南省博物館) in the city of Changsha. The burial complex of Mawangdui includes three graves belonging to three members of the family of the Marquis of Dai 軾 and Chancellor of the Kingdom of Changsha, Li Cang 利蒼, who lived during the early years of the Han 漢 Dynasty (202 BCE–220 CE). Li Cang occupied tomb n. 2, his wife Xin Zhui 辛追, tomb n. 1, and one of their sons, whose name is unknown, tomb n. 3, where the two Laozi manuscripts have been found. Thanks to an inventory slip found inside the tomb, it is known that it has been sealed in the year 168 BCE. A large number of silk texts, philosophical, astronomical, military, and medical in content (to mention a few), were found inside a lacquered box inside the tomb, totaling about 120000 written words. Some of the manuscripts were already known to the tradition, such as the case of the two Laozi, the Yijing 易經 (Classic of changes) found within the same tomb, along with various commentaries related to it, and a copy of the Zhanguo ce 戰國策 (Annals of the Warring States), while others represent texts unknown until the time of the excavation or known only by their title. As regards the two Laozi, these are two versions that are roughly complete with respect to the transmitted text, and they are more alike to each other than to any other edition of the Daodejing, but they still exhibit a few discrepancies. They are referred to as Laozi A (jia 甲) and Laozi B (yi 乙), and both present various lacunae due to damage to the material support, to a greater extent in the case of manuscript A. What principally distinguishes these two versions from the transmitted text is the inversion of the two macro-sections that make up the Daodejing: meaning that, in both Mawangdui texts, the De 德 (virtue) section precedes the Dao 道 (way) section, as is also the case for the Peking University bamboo slips version of the Laozi (Hanjianben Laozi 漢簡本老子), acquired by Peking University in 2009, and dated around the reign of Emperor Wu 武 (156 – 87 BCE). Manuscript B even presents the characters De and Dao as the titles in the openings of the two sections, followed by the total number of characters, thus giving the impression that the two sections were perceived as two distinct texts. The reverse order of the two macro-sections resulted in the two manuscripts found in Mawangdui also being referred to as Dedaojing 德道經. The order of passages also varies slightly from the textus receptus. Taking the chapters of the transmitted Daodejing as a reference, the order found in the Mawangdui manuscripts is: 38-39, 41, 40, 42-66, 80-81, 67-79 (De) and 1-21, 24, 22-23, 25-37 (Dao). The sequence of the passages follows the same order in both manuscript editions. Compared to the textus receptus, some verses are incomplete, or present lexical and graphic variants – not always identical between the two editions A and B. Moreover, Mawangdui texts include a greater number of grammatical words than the transmitted Daodejing: an example is the far more frequent use of the appositional sentence final particle ye 也. Of the two manuscripts, Laozi A is earlier and dated roughly between 221 and 206 BCE; Laozi B is dated around 206-194 BCE (during the reign of Liu Bang 劉邦, emperor Gao Zu 高祖 of the Han). In support of these dating hypotheses, Laozi A is written in the Qin 秦 dynasty (221-206 BCE) xiaozhuan 小篆 (small seal) calligraphic style, while Laozi B is written in the lishu 隸書 (clerical script) calligraphic style. Furthermore, text B avoids the use of Liu Bang's name characters, employing guo 國 as a synonym for bang 邦. Yet, it does not avoid neither ying 盈 nor heng 恆, from Liu Ying and Liu Heng's

names. Text A does not present such avoidance, reinforcing the hypothesis that it must have been transcribed before 206 BCE. Although the two versions are very similar to each other, some variations in wording (beyond the already mentioned tabooed words in manuscript B) are present. To cite a few examples: the second verse of the received chapter 46 in Mawangdui A reads 天下無道戎馬生於郊, while Mawangdui B reads 道戎馬生於郊, with no repetition of tianxia 天下, already present in the preceding verse, and the passage goes on reading 非莫大於可欲 in A, and 非莫大可欲 in B, with the omission of yu 於; the closing verse of received chapter 16 appears in manuscript A as 沕身不怠, and in manuscript B as 道乃沒身不殆, with either wu 沕 or mei 沒, and dai 怠 or dai 殆. Several orthographic inconsistencies suggest that manuscripts A and B may have been written by different scribes. Neither manuscript includes a systematic division into chapters and neither of them numbers them. Nevertheless, manuscript A presents a more systematized use of punctuation: comma-like strokes on the bottom right side of characters, that seems to signal a pause, and bigger dots in the center of a line at the beginning of longer textual sections that sometimes correspond to the division into chapters of the textus receptus. Laozi B only uses the comma-like stroke and does it sporadically. In some instances, chapters that are separate in the received Daodejing seem to be conceived as a continuous piece in the Mawangdui manuscripts. For example, the passage corresponding to chapter 68 from the received text starts with gu 故 (therefore) in Laozi B – indicating the connection with the preceding passage. Both the absence of a precise chapter division, particularly in Manuscript B, and the reverse order of the De and Dao sections have led scholars to question what the original structure of the text must have been. The division of the textus receptus into chapters could represent a later alteration by the commentators, but at the same time, the presence of punctuation marks that seem to signal in some way the partition between some sections in Laozi A would lead one to think that by the time that the manuscript was transcribed, some subdivisions must have already taken form. As regards the inverted order of the De and Dao sections, it could on the one hand represent a marginal issue, related to a misunderstanding in the sequence of transcription of the texts, but it could also indicate the existence, by the second century BCE, of two distinct textual traditions: one characterized by the Dao-de sequence and one by the De-Dao sequence. Even the very coexistence of two such similar manuscripts within the same burial prompts questions about their origins: it is still unclear whether these are two separate elaborations of the same original text. The two Laozi are inked on two separate silk scrolls along with other works. As for manuscript A, it is followed by four Confucian texts, while manuscript B follows a group of Huanglao 黃老 texts, known by the title Huangdi sijing 黃帝四經 (Four Classics of the Yellow Emperor). Laozi A is written on a silk cloth of about 350 cm (with the Laozi itself occupying around 170 cm in length), while Laozi B silk cloth is around 165 cm long.

Date Range: 221 BCE - 194 BCE

Region: Mawangdui Han Tombs

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

Mawangdui Han Tombs

Status of Readership:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Mawangdui Hanmu boshu 馬王堆漢墓帛書, Wenwu chubanshe, 1980.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/mawangdui>
- Source 1 Description: Mawangdui Laozi (Chinese text project)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/mawangdui>
- Source 1 Description: Mawangdui Laozi (Chinese text project)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Silk

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- Yes

Tomb

- Yes

Notes: The two manuscripts have been found by archaeologists inside a Western Han tomb in the village of Mawangdui, near the city of Changsha. The occupant of the tomb (named tomb

n. 3) was one of the sons of the Marquis of Dai.

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: Hunan Provincial Museum (湖南省博物館) in the city of Changsha

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Despite the Daodejing being considered part of the so-called "Daoist Canon" of the Religious Daoism (Daojiao 道教), there is no evidence that the early manuscripts had a similar function.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Robinet (1991) claims that the poetic form of the received text suggests that it was believed that it could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition and it was therefore intended to be memorized and sung.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text is not accompanied by art, but in the burial complex of Mawangdui many art pieces have been found: elegant funerary equipments, lacquer objects, maps, diagrams, and silk banners.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Mawangdui Laozi A and B are two different silk manuscripts representing early versions of the book later known as Daodejing. Besides the text transmitted by tradition with different commentaries, there are also other manuscript versions (e.g., Guodian Laozi on bamboo (郭店老子 A, B, C), Han Laozi on bamboo (Hanjianben Laozi 漢簡本老子), the version from Dunhuang 敦煌).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: These two manuscripts are part of the Mawangdui corpus of excavated silk manuscripts. Furthermore, they have been written in the same silk scrolls with other texts: confucian texts as regards Laozi A; the Huangdi sijing 皇帝四經 as regards Laozi B.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: philosophical tradition

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: none

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The passages corresponding to received 31 in both manuscript A and B refer to funerary rites and explain how to deal with the people who die in the battlefield to honor them.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: No supreme high god is explicitly mentioned in the text.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The manuscripts refer, in a general way, to both shen 神 and gui 鬼.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Yes

Notes: The texts refer to an important sacrifice celebrated in honor of spirits and ancestors, the Tai lao 大牢, in which cattle, pigs, and sheep were offered.

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: The texts do not provide precise information about these spirits.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
 - Specify: Not specified.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: While the texts themselves do not guide divination practices, S. Allan claims that the use of the word shi 式 in the Laozi refers to the divination tool (shipan 式盤).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The texts do not advocate any particular virtues; on the contrary, the Laozi strongly distances itself from the so-called Confucian virtues (such as benevolence, dedication to study, righteousness, etc.). Nonetheless, the term De 德, which can be translated as "virtue," is central to the transmitted text and the manuscript editions as well (beyond being explicitly used as the title of the first macro-section of Laozi B): however, this indicates the virtue or potency derived directly from the Dao itself.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The texts do not address the readers using fictive kinship terminology, but the term mu 母 (mother) is employed in reference to the Dao 道 itself. For example, in sentences such: 可以為天地母; 天下有始，以為天下母; 有國之母，可以長久.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: These two manuscripts, as well as other editions related to the Daodejing tradition, stand out against all forms of war.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Food Production

- Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?
– No

Bibliography

General References

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